

PROBLEMS OF RESOCIALIZATION OF WOMEN AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: In this article, as a way to fight against crime, the necessity of resocialization of persons released from penal institutions, the importance of the principle of differentiation in the process of re-socialization, the specific aspects of working with ex-convict women, the problems they face and ways to overcome them analyzed as a result of studying the experience of different foreign countries. As a result of these analyses, suggestions and recommendations were developed to eliminate the identified problems.

Keywords: post-penitentiary system, women released from correctional institutions, resocialization, recidivism, probation, resocialization programs.

One of the important tasks of the state is to protect law and order in society, fight crime and prevent crimes by identifying the factors that cause them. Therefore, the areas of criminal law, penal law, criminology and crime prevention are always in the spotlight, and scientific research is constantly being conducted to identify and eliminate problems in this area. The state is developing regulatory legal documents at various levels aimed at legal regulation of relations in this area.

At the same time, large-scale reforms to reduce crime are constantly being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to the information provided on the official page of the Statistics Agency, the total number of registered crimes in 2020 was 62081, in 2021 -

111082, in 2022 - 105215. From this we see that the crime rate is increasing every year. This shows that the measures taken must be strengthened.

One of these measures is to improve resocialization of persons released from penal institutions. Through this, it is possible to reduce the rate of re-offending and recidivism by them.

It is known that there are a number of problems that need to be solved in the postpenitentiary system, that is, a number of problems will arise in front of individuals after serving their sentence. In order to study and analyze these problems in detail, it is appropriate to study the persons released from penal institutions by dividing them into the categories of women, men, and minors based on the principle of differentiation.

This article discusses the problems of social adaptation of women released from correctional institutions, and also develops proposals and recommendations to eliminate these problems and thereby reduce the level of recidivism on their part.

The total number of reported crimes committed by women was 5,774 in 2020, 9,759 in 2021, and 11,460 in 2022. This shows that female crime is increasing sharply.

Although it was not possible to obtain information on how many of these women were sentenced to imprisonment, according to the information provided by the Special Accounting Department of the Department of Corrections, in 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022 and In 2023, 731, 825, 601, 560, 693 and 709 women were released from penal institutions, respectively[1].

It can be seen that the state is faced with the task of reintegrating 700 women into society every year. The most effective way to solve this problem is to work with each former convict individually. Only then will it be possible to fully identify the problems that are bothering them and eliminate those problems. Here, in general, we should dwell on the question of what problems arise for women who

have served their sentences, and the circumstances that impede their resocialization and reduce the possibility of committing a crime.

The criminal past of former convicts is one of the main factors hindering their resocialization. In addition to the difficulties women face in prison, they face stigma and discrimination when they are released and returned to society. It is because of their criminal history that women often face negative attitudes, prejudices and discrimination from society. This creates problems for them in finding work, housing and social reintegration. Most women after their release will not be able to find stable housing and work, as well as support from the state, civil society institutions and relatives. These factors can make it difficult to establish a stable life and increase the risk of relapse.

The next factor is problems arising in family relationships. Successful resocialization depends on the existence of a safe, stable family environment and active support from family members after release. However, once women are released, this support is often unavailable to them. Women's deprivation of liberty leads to family breakdown in most cases, including divorce, unemployment and homelessness[2]. When women are in prison, even for a short period of time, their children are often forced to live with other relatives or receive alternative care. In such situations, it is sometimes difficult to reunite families after release.

The next issue is the obstacles to women's employment. Having a steady job after release and being able to meet financial needs is critical to preventing recidivism. But women convicts often face difficulties in finding a job due to their lack of qualifications, education and the stigma associated with their criminal past. The resulting financial instability can exacerbate problems related to housing, education, and health.

In addition, insufficient access to health care, including reproductive health services, can cause serious problems for women's socialization.

The above-mentioned issues are not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the whole world related to resocialization. In order to overcome these and create effective re-socialization programs and support services tailored to the needs of women offenders around the world, it is essential to recognize and address these issues.

If we look at the example of Uzbekistan, the mechanism for the effective functioning of the post-penitentiary system has not been sufficiently formed, that is, the normative legal document has not been developed that comprehensively regulates the relations related to the re-socialization of persons who have served their sentence. Also practice in this field is not fully formed. In addition, the activities of civil society institutions in this field have not been established.

However, it is necessary to mention some structures that carry out the task of re-socializing persons who have served their sentence. Probation service, rehabilitation and social adaptation centers for persons released from places of deprivation of liberty established by the authorities are among them. The probation service is a relatively new structure in Uzbekistan, and its main focus is on the execution of sentences not related to deprivation of liberty, and serious attention is not paid to the resocialization of prisoners. The reason is that the disproportion between the workload of the Probation Service and the state units does not allow this.

If we consider the activities of rehabilitation and social adaptation centers for persons released from places of imprisonment, then their main task is to organize and ensure social protection of persons released from places of imprisonment, clothing, food and accommodation in conditions to properly satisfy their primary needs by providing a one-time benefit, create acceptable social and living conditions, receive help from specialists (psychologist, medical worker, lawyer, etc.), provide treatment, referral to homes for the elderly and disabled[3]. Although it is defined as providing assistance in solving housing and other social

problems, as well as in obtaining benefits provided by law, as a result of visiting relevant places and studying, it turned out that the main activity of the center is one-time benefits to former convicts. From the above, we can conclude that in Uzbekistan there are a number of issues that need to be resolved not only in terms of the reintegration into society of women who have served their sentences, but also in the entire post-penitentiary system.

Above, we explained a number of problems that may arise in the process of women's resocialization, now let's analyze the methods of eliminating these problems. In the implementation of women's resocialization, different countries develop specific socialization programs, including programs aimed at treatment, education, vocational training, and psychological support.

If we look at the example of Canada, in order to facilitate the future integration of prisoners into society in penal institutions, a number of activities are carried out while they are serving their sentences, including the active use of public participation, that is, voluntary citizens visiting penal institutions, they teach their skills and abilities to prisoners. In addition, the visit of various families to the penal institutions is also envisaged, the purpose of which is to prevent the prisoners from being cut off from society and social life and the problems that may arise in the process of their re-socialization in the future[4].

The postpenitentiary system is well established in Russia. Special assistance centers have been established for women who have served their sentence. This center is called Women's Aid Crisis Centers and it is financed by the state. The main goal of the center is to provide psychological support to women who have been in difficult social conditions, and to help them re-socialize. The center provides medical, psychological, economic and legal services[4]. The positive side of the center is that all the services listed above are provided in one place, which prevents excessive wandering of ex-convicts.

Finland is one of the countries with high experience in re-socialization of persons who have served their sentences[5, 6]. Rather than punishing criminals, Finland prioritizes preparing them for life after release, meaning that prisoners are offered quality education and vocational training that ensures a smooth transition to the outside world. . In addition, special attention is paid to family relations and parental support in women's prisons. After their release, they will have the opportunity to use various social services through the probation service.

The countries that we have discussed above and a number of other developed countries also do not punish convicts at the stage of execution of the sentence, but prepare them for freedom as their main goal, in which they can learn a profession, get an education, and execute the sentence. It allows them to maintain family relations in a certain sense despite being in the institution. Through this, they will be able to continue their life in the society without difficulties after their release. As we have seen above, these measures are carried out in parallel not only by the state, but also by non-governmental organizations. This will ensure more effective re-socialization of persons who have served their sentence.

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